

Model Transformation Patterns in MDDPlatform

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16938253

This document is supplementary material accompanying the paper titled "Microservice-based model-driven architecture for implementing modeling and model-transformation as a service". This document provides a detailed description of model transformation patterns implemented in the MDDPlatform microservices. It covers transformation categories such as Object-to-Object, Object-to-Concept, Relational Dimension, and Model-to-Text mappings. Each pattern is explained with its purpose, parameters, solution steps, and usage examples, serving as a reference for implementing reusable transformations.

1. Model Transformation Patterns

In this section, we will introduce the model transformation patterns with details. Table 32 shows the information of the patterns that have been identified and implemented in the model transformations microservice.

Table 1: List of Model Transformation Patterns

No.	Pattern	Category	Description
1	Map Instance	Object2Object	Mapping an instance of the input model to an instance with the same name and type in the output model
2	Map One To One	Object2Object	Mapping an instance of a concept in the input model to an instance of another concept with the same name, but a different type, in the output model
3	Map One To One With Properties	Object2Object	Mapping an instance of a concept in the input model to an instance with the same name, but a different type in the output model and valuing its attributes
4	Map One To Two	Object2Object	Mapping the instances of one concept in the input model to the instances of two concepts in the output model
5	Map Related Objects	Object2Object	Mapping instances of two related concepts in the input model to the instances of the corresponding concepts in the output model
6	Merge Domain Object Models	Object2Object	Merging the information of two input models into one output model
7	Replace Relation With Chain Of Nodes	Object2Object	Mapping instances of two related concepts in the input model to a triple chain of related objects in the output model
8	Replace Relation With Fork Node	Object2Object	Converting the relationship between two related concepts in the input model to a node in the output model
9	Set Relational Dimension	Object2Object	Setting a relationship (Relational Dimension) between the domain objects of a model at the lower level of abstraction with the domain concept of a model at the higher level of abstraction
10	Convert Instance To Type	Object2Concept	Converting the instances of a concept in the input model to the new concepts, with the same name, in the output model
11	Extract Operation Attribute From Chain Of Nodes	Object2Concept	Extracting the operations of a domain concept and the attributes of those operations from a chain of three domain objects.
12	Extract Operation From Chain Of Nodes	Object2Concept	Extracting the operations of a domain concept from a chain of three domain objects.
13	Extract Operation From One To One To Many Relation	Object2Concept	Extracting operations defined in a domain concept from a one-to-one-to-many relationship defined between domain objects
14	Map Object Property To Concept Attribute	Object2Concept	Mapping the properties of a domain object and its values to the attributes of a domain concept and its values
15	Replace Association With Relation	Object2Concept	Defining a new relationship in the domain concepts model, based on the existing relationship between domain objects

16	Replace Relation With Action	Object2Concept	Convert a relationship to an action (an operation without output)
17	Replace Relation With Concept Attribute	Object2Concept	Converting a relationship into attributes of a concept
18	Replace Relation With Generic Property	Object2Concept	Converting a relation to the concept property
19	Replace Relation With Operation	Object2Concept	Converting the relation to the operation of a concept
20	Replace Relation With Operation Attributes	Object2Concept	Converting the relationship into the operation of a concept and assigning the attribute to that operation
21	Replace Relation With Property	Object2Concept	Convert the relation to a primitive type property
22	Copy Upstream Node Property To Downstream Node Relation	RelationalDimension	Converting properties of upstream model concepts to objects and relationships between them in the downstream model
23	Copy Upstream Node Relation To Downstream Node Relation	RelationalDimension	Converting relationships between concepts in the upstream model to objects and relationships between them in the downstream model
24	Merge Upstream Node Property With Downstream Node Relation	RelationalDimension	Combining properties and relations of upstream model concepts with relations of domain objects in the downstream model, in the form of new properties in the output model
25	Merge Upstream Node With Downstream Node	RelationalDimension	Combining the operations and properties of upstream domain concepts model and downstream domain objects models, in the form of the properties and operations of new concepts in the output model
26	Merge Upstream Node With Downstream Node Property As Attribute	RelationalDimension	Combining the operations and properties of the upstream domain concepts model and downstream domain objects models, in the form of operations, properties and attributes of new concepts in the output model
27	Replace Relational Dimension With Source Node Relation	RelationalDimension	Replacing the relational dimension between the downstream model and the upstream model with new objects and relationships in the downstream model
28	Set Higher Dimension Relation	RelationalDimension	Setting the relational dimension of the domain objects of the downstream model at the lower level of abstraction, based on the domain objects of the upstream model at a higher level
29	Append Line Of String For Each One To Many Relation	Model2Text	Converting the information of related objects in a one-to-many relationship into a string and inserting it into the text
30	Generate C# Code Of Class Concept	Model2Text	Converting the information of a concept corresponding to a class to the definition code of a Class in C# language
31	Generate C# Code Of Interface Concept	Model2Text	Converting the information of a concept corresponding to the interface to the definition code of an Interface in C# language

Example

Figure 1: Input Model

Figure 2: Output Model

1.2. Map One To One

Table 3: Pattern Definition: Map One To One

Map One To One			
Title	Mapping an instance of a concept in the input model to an instance of another concept with the same name, but a different type, in the output model		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)		
Problem	The same concept may be described with different names in two different models, but the objects derived from this concept in the first model correspond to an object with the same name in the second model. Having instances of that concept in the first model, we need to create corresponding instances (not necessarily of the same type) in the second model.		
Parameters	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. 2. The desired concept in the input model 3. 3. The output model (second model) </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The desired concept in the output model 5. The expression for calculating the instances name in the output model </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. 2. The desired concept in the input model 3. 3. The output model (second model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The desired concept in the output model 5. The expression for calculating the instances name in the output model
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. 2. The desired concept in the input model 3. 3. The output model (second model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The desired concept in the output model 5. The expression for calculating the instances name in the output model 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Retrieving domain objects instantiating from the desired concept in the first model 2. For each of the objects identified in the previous step, do the following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Based on the information of the object mentioned in step 2 and using parameter 5 of the problem model, we calculate the name of the corresponding object in the second model. b) In the second model, we create an object whose name is equal to the value obtained in step (2.a) and whose type is equal to the value of parameter 4 of the problem model. 		
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Object/MapOneToOne Method: POST Request body : <pre> { "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "source": string, "outputModel": guid, "destination": string, "instanceNameExpression": string } </pre>		

Example

Table 4: Map One To One: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
Source	Aggregate.Concept
Destination	Repository.Concept
InstanceNameExpression	Source.Name+Repository

Figure 3: Input Model

Figure 4: Output Model

1.3. Map One To One with Properties

Table 5: Pattern Definition: Map One To One with Properties

Map One To One with Properties			
Title	Mapping an instance of a concept in the input model to an instance with the same name, but a different type in the output model and valuing its attributes		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)		
Problem	We want to define a mapping between the instances of a concept in the first model with the instances of a concept in the second model so that the attributes and characteristics of the corresponding instances in the second model can be quantified based on the attributes and characteristics of these instances in the first model.		
Parameters	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The desired concept in the first model 3. The output model (second model) </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The desired concept in the second model 5. Key-value pair (name, value expression) for the desired concept in the second model </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The desired concept in the first model 3. The output model (second model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The desired concept in the second model 5. Key-value pair (name, value expression) for the desired concept in the second model
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The desired concept in the first model 3. The output model (second model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The desired concept in the second model 5. Key-value pair (name, value expression) for the desired concept in the second model 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Retrieving domain objects arising from the desired concept in the first model 2. For each of the objects identified in the previous step, do the following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) An object with the same name but based on the desired concept in the second model is created. b) We calculate the attribute values of the new object based on the characteristics and attributes of the object mentioned in step 2. c) For the object created in the second model (2.a), we adjust the attribute values based on the information of the previous step (2.b). 		
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Object/MapOneToOneWithProperties Method: POST Request body : <pre> { "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "source": string, "outputModel": guid, "destination": guid, "destinationMembers": [{ "name": string, "valueExpression": string }] }</pre>		

Example

Table 6: Map One To One with Properties: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value	
Source	CommandHandler.Concept	
Destination	BaseClass.Concept	
DestinationMembers	Name	Value Expression
	Namespace	OnlineShop.Commands.Handlers
	IsStatic	false
	IsAbstract	false
	Visibility	public
	Extend	ICommandHandler<+Source.canHandle(Command.Concept)+>

Figure 5: Input model

Figure 6: Output Model

1.4. Map One To Two

Table 7: Pattern Definition: Map One To Two

Map One To Two			
Title	Mapping the instances of one concept in the input model to the instances of two concepts in the output model		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)		
Problem	We want to map the instances of a concept in the input model to the instances of two different concepts in the output model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The source node in the input model 4. The first destination node in the output model 5. The second destination node in the output model 6. The expression for resolving the name of an instance of the first destination </td> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The expression for resolving the name of an instance of the second destination 8. The expression for resolving the property and property value of an instance of the first destination 9. The expression for resolving the property and property value of an instance of the second destination </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The source node in the input model 4. The first destination node in the output model 5. The second destination node in the output model 6. The expression for resolving the name of an instance of the first destination 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The expression for resolving the name of an instance of the second destination 8. The expression for resolving the property and property value of an instance of the first destination 9. The expression for resolving the property and property value of an instance of the second destination
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The source node in the input model 4. The first destination node in the output model 5. The second destination node in the output model 6. The expression for resolving the name of an instance of the first destination 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The expression for resolving the name of an instance of the second destination 8. The expression for resolving the property and property value of an instance of the first destination 9. The expression for resolving the property and property value of an instance of the second destination 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Object2Object/MapOneToTwo Method: POST Request body :</p> <pre> { "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "source": string, "firstDestination": string, "firstDestinationInstanceNameExpression": string, "secondDestination": string, "secondDestinationInstanceNameExpression": string, "firstToSecondRelationName": string, "firstDestinationMembers": [{ "name": string, "valueExpression": string }], "secondDestinationMembers": [{ "name": string, "valueExpression": string }], "outputModel": guid } </pre>		

1.5. Map Related Objects

Table 8: Pattern Definition: Map Related Objects

Map Related Objects			
Title	Mapping instances of two related concepts in the input model to the instances of the corresponding concepts in the output model		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)		
Problem	We want to map the instances of two related concepts in the first model to the instances of two corresponding concepts with a specific relationship in the second model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The output model (second model) 6. The source node in the second model 7. The destination node in the second model </td> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the second model 9. The name expression, for the instance created from the source node in the second model 10. The name expression, for the instance created from the destination node in the second model </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The output model (second model) 6. The source node in the second model 7. The destination node in the second model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the second model 9. The name expression, for the instance created from the source node in the second model 10. The name expression, for the instance created from the destination node in the second model
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The output model (second model) 6. The source node in the second model 7. The destination node in the second model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the second model 9. The name expression, for the instance created from the source node in the second model 10. The name expression, for the instance created from the destination node in the second model 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of the parameters (2, 3, and 4), we identify a set of related objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of multiples (Source, Relation, and Destination). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do the following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) With the help of the name expression (parameter 9) and tuple information, we determine the name of the instance corresponding to the source node and create a domain object with this name in the second model. This object is derived from the concept determined in the parameter 6. b) With the help of the name expression (parameter 10) and tuple information, we determine the name of the instance corresponding to the destination node and create a domain object with this name in the second model. This object is derived from the concept determined in the parameter 7. c) We define the relationship (parameter 8) between the objects created in paragraphs (2.a, 2.b). 		
How to use	url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Object/MapRelatedObjects Method: POST Request body : <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "inputSource": string, "inputDestination": string, "inputSourceToDestinationRelation": string, "outputModel": guid, "outputSource": string, "outputDestination": string, "outputSourceToDestinationRelation": string, "outputSourceInstanceExpression": string, "outputDestinationInstanceExpression": string }</pre>		

Example

Table 9: Map Related Objects: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
InputSource	DomainConcept.Concept
InputDestination	Event.Concept
InputSourceToDestinationRelation	isInterestedIn
OutputSource	EventHandler.Concept
OutputDestination	Event.Concept
OutputSourceToDestinationRelation	canHandle
OutputSourceInstanceExpression	InputDestination.Name+Handler
OutputDestinationInstanceExpression	InputDestination.Name

Figure 7: Input Model

Figure 8: Output Model

1.6. Merge Domain Object Models

Table 10: Pattern Definition: Merge Domain Object Models

Merge Domain Object Models					
Title	Merging the information of two input models into one output model				
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)				
Problem	We want to combine the data from two input models into a single output model.				
Parameters	<table border="1"><tr><td>1. The first input model</td><td>3. The output model</td></tr><tr><td>2. The second input model</td><td></td></tr></table>	1. The first input model	3. The output model	2. The second input model	
1. The first input model	3. The output model				
2. The second input model					
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Object2Object/MergerDomainObjectModels Method: POST Request body : { "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "firstModel": guid, "secondModel": guid, "outputModel": guid }				

1.7. Replace Relation with Chain of Nodes

Table 11: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Chain of Nodes

Replace Relation with Chain of Nodes			
Title	Mapping instances of two related concepts in the input model to a triple chain of related objects in the output model		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)		
Problem	We want to map the instances of two related concepts in the first model to the instances of a triple chain of concepts with a specific relationship in the second model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first model (input model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The second model (output model) 6. The first node in the second model 7. The middle node in the second model </td> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The last node in the second model 9. Title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node in the second model 10. Title of the relationship from the middle node to the last node in the second model 11. The expression, for resolving the name of the instance created from the first node 12. The expression for resolving the name of the instance created from the middle node 13. The expression for resolving the name of the instance created from the last node </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first model (input model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The second model (output model) 6. The first node in the second model 7. The middle node in the second model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The last node in the second model 9. Title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node in the second model 10. Title of the relationship from the middle node to the last node in the second model 11. The expression, for resolving the name of the instance created from the first node 12. The expression for resolving the name of the instance created from the middle node 13. The expression for resolving the name of the instance created from the last node
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The first model (input model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The second model (output model) 6. The first node in the second model 7. The middle node in the second model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The last node in the second model 9. Title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node in the second model 10. Title of the relationship from the middle node to the last node in the second model 11. The expression, for resolving the name of the instance created from the first node 12. The expression for resolving the name of the instance created from the middle node 13. The expression for resolving the name of the instance created from the last node 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of the parameters 2, 3, and 4, we identify a set of related objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of a tuple (Source, Relation, and Destination). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) With the help of the name expressions in the parameters 11, 12 and 13 and tuple information, we determine the names of the instances corresponding to the first, middle and last nodes and create the corresponding objects. b) We define the relationship between the first node and the middle node, and the middle node and the last node based on the information in the parameters 9 and 10. 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Object/ReplaceRelationWithChainOfNodes</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body : {</p> <pre style="margin-left: 20px;"> "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelation": string, "outputModel": guid, "firstNode": string, "middleNode": string, "lastNode": string, "firstToMiddleNodeRelation": string, "middleToLastNodeRelation": string, "firstNodeInstanceExpression": string, "middleNodeInstanceExpression": string, "lastNodeInstanceExpression": string </pre> <p>}</p>		

Example

Table 12: Replace Relation with Chain of Nodes: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	ApiController.Concept
DestinationNode	Command.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelation	dispatchCommand
FirstNode	ApiController.Concept
MiddleNode	HTTPPost.Endpoint.Concept
LastNode	Command.Concept
FirstToMiddleNodeRelation	hasEndpoint
MiddleToLastNodeRelation	hasRequestBody
FirstNodeInstanceExpression	SourceNode.Name
MiddleNodeInstanceExpression	DestinationNode.Name+Endpoint
LastNodeInstanceExpression	DestinationNode.Name

Figure 9: Input Model

Figure 10: Output Model

1.8. Replace Relation with Fork Node

Table 13: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Fork Node

Replace Relation with Fork Node			
Title	Converting the relationship between two related concepts in the input model to a node in the output model		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)		
Problem	We want to have instances with the same name in the second model corresponding to the instances of two related concepts in the first model. But the relationship between these instances in the first model should be replaced by an instance of a third node in the second model. In other words, a relationship between two concepts in the first model becomes two relationships between three concepts in the second model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The output model (second model) </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The third node in the second model 7. The relationship from the third node to the source node in the second model 8. The relationship from the third node to the destination node in the second model 9. The expression, for resolving the name of the instance created from the third node </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The output model (second model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The third node in the second model 7. The relationship from the third node to the source node in the second model 8. The relationship from the third node to the destination node in the second model 9. The expression, for resolving the name of the instance created from the third node
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 5. The output model (second model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The third node in the second model 7. The relationship from the third node to the source node in the second model 8. The relationship from the third node to the destination node in the second model 9. The expression, for resolving the name of the instance created from the third node 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of parameters 2, 3, and 4, we identify a set of related objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of tuple (Source, Relation, and Destination). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) With the help of the expression in parameter 9 and tuple information, we determine the name of the instance corresponding to the third node and create the corresponding object. b) Based on the information of parameters 7 and 8 and tuple information, we obtain the type of source and destination nodes in the second model and create the corresponding examples with the same names as the first model. c) Using the information in parameter 7 and 8, we establish the relationship between the object created in step 2.a with the two objects created in step 2.b. 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Object/ReplaceRelationWithForkNode</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelation": string, "outputModel": guid, "forkNode": string, "forkToSourceRelation": string, "forkToDestinationRelation": string, "forkNodeInstanceExpression": string, }</pre>		

Example

Table 14: Replace Relation with Fork Node: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	Command.Concept
DestinationNode	Event.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelation	canPublish
ForkNode	CommandHandler
ForkToSourceRelation	handle
ForkToDestinationRelation	publish
ForkNodeInstanceExpression	SourceNode.Name+Handler

Figure 11: Input Model

Figure 12: Output Model

1.9. Set Relational Dimension

Table 15: Pattern Definition: Set Relational Dimension

Set Relational Dimension			
Title	Setting a relationship (Relational Dimension) between the domain objects of a model at the lower level of abstraction with the domain concept of a model at the higher level of abstraction		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into another domain objects model(Object2Object)		
Problem	We want to establish a connection between the domain objects of a model at a lower level of abstraction and the domain concept of a model at a higher level of abstraction, which is known as a Relational Dimension.		
Parameters	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (that is the output model at the same time) 2. The type of domain object in the input model (output model) </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The expression for resolving the name of the Relational Dimension 4. The expression for resolving the target of the Relational Dimension </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (that is the output model at the same time) 2. The type of domain object in the input model (output model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The expression for resolving the name of the Relational Dimension 4. The expression for resolving the target of the Relational Dimension
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (that is the output model at the same time) 2. The type of domain object in the input model (output model) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. The expression for resolving the name of the Relational Dimension 4. The expression for resolving the target of the Relational Dimension 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Object2Object/SetRelationalDimension</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "element": string, "relationNameExpression": string, "relationTargetExpression": string }</pre>		

1.10. Convert Instance to Type

Table 16: Pattern Definition: Convert Instance to Type

Convert Instance to Type									
Title	Converting the instances of a concept in the input model to the new concepts, with the same name, in the output model								
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)								
Problem	We want to define new concepts in the output model by using instances of a concept in the input model so that it is possible to instantiate these new concepts, again.								
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">1. The input model (first model)</td> <td style="width: 50%;">a) Preserve type</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Type of instances in the first model</td> <td>b) Preserve properties</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. The output model (second model)</td> <td>c) Preserve relations</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. A set of configuration parameters:</td> <td>d) Preserve operations</td> </tr> </table>	1. The input model (first model)	a) Preserve type	2. Type of instances in the first model	b) Preserve properties	3. The output model (second model)	c) Preserve relations	4. A set of configuration parameters:	d) Preserve operations
1. The input model (first model)	a) Preserve type								
2. Type of instances in the first model	b) Preserve properties								
3. The output model (second model)	c) Preserve relations								
4. A set of configuration parameters:	d) Preserve operations								
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Retrieving domain objects instantiating from the desired concept (parameter 2) in the first model 2. For each of the objects obtained in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Based on the value of the parameter (4.a), we specify the type of this concept. b. We specify the name of the concept from the name of the object in step 2. c. If there is no concept with the name and type specified in steps (2.a) and (2.b) in the second model, we will define it. d. Based on the configuration parameter value (4.b), we define the properties of this concept. e. Based on the value of the configuration parameter (4.d), we define the operations of this concept. 								
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ConvertInstanceToType</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "typeOfInstance": string, "outputModel": guid, "preserveType": bool, "preserveProperties": bool, "preserveRelations": bool, "preserveOperations": bool }</pre>								

Example

Table 17: Convert Instance to Type: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
TypeOfInstance	CommandHandler.Concept
PreserveType	true
PreserveProperties	false
PreserveRelations	true
PreserveOperations	false

Figure 13: Input model

Figure 14: Output model

1.11. Extract Operation Attribute from Chain of Nodes

Table 18: Pattern Definition: Extract Operation Attribute from Chain of Nodes

Extract Operation Attribute from Chain of Nodes			
Title	Extracting the operations of a domain concept and the attributes of those operations from a chain of three domain objects.		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to extract the attributes and operations of a domain concept from a chain of three domain objects		
Parameters	<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node. 7. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last node </td> <td style="vertical-align: top; padding-left: 20px;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The expression for resolving the name of the domain concept 9. The expression for resolving the type of the domain concept 10. The expression for resolving the name of the concept operation 11. The expression for resolving the name of the attribute 12. The expression for resolving the value of the attribute </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node. 7. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The expression for resolving the name of the domain concept 9. The expression for resolving the type of the domain concept 10. The expression for resolving the name of the concept operation 11. The expression for resolving the name of the attribute 12. The expression for resolving the value of the attribute
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node. 7. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The expression for resolving the name of the domain concept 9. The expression for resolving the type of the domain concept 10. The expression for resolving the name of the concept operation 11. The expression for resolving the name of the attribute 12. The expression for resolving the value of the attribute 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Object2Concept/ExtractOperationAttributeFromChainOfNodes</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "firstNode": string, "middleNode": string, "lastNode": string, "firstToMiddleNodeRelation": string, "middleToLastNodeRelation": string, "outputModel": guid, "conceptNameExpression": string, "conceptTypeExpression": string, "operationNameExpression": string, "attributeNameExpression": string, "attributeValueExpression": string }</pre>		

1.12. Extract Operation from Chain of Nodes

Table 19: Pattern Definition: Extract Operation from Chain of Nodes

Extract Operation from Chain of Nodes			
Title	Extracting the operations of a domain concept from a chain of three domain objects.		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to extract the operations of a domain concept from a sequence of three domain objects.		
Parameters	<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of relationship form the first node to the middle node 7. The title of relationship form the middle node to the last node </td> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 9. The expression for resolving the input parameters of the operation 10. The expression for resolving the output type of the operation 11. The expression for resolving the multiplicity of the output </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of relationship form the first node to the middle node 7. The title of relationship form the middle node to the last node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 9. The expression for resolving the input parameters of the operation 10. The expression for resolving the output type of the operation 11. The expression for resolving the multiplicity of the output
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of relationship form the first node to the middle node 7. The title of relationship form the middle node to the last node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 9. The expression for resolving the input parameters of the operation 10. The expression for resolving the output type of the operation 11. The expression for resolving the multiplicity of the output 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Object2Concept/ExtractOperationFromChainOfNodes</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "firstNode": string, "middleNode": string, "lastNode": string, "firstToMiddleNodeRelation": string, "middleToLastNodeRelation": string, "operationNameExpression": string, "operationInputsExpression": string, "operationOutputTypeExpression": string, "operationOutputMultiplicityExpression": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

1.13. Extract Operation from One to One to Many Relation

Table 20: Pattern Definition: Extract Operation from One to One to Many Relation

Extract Operation from One to One to Many Relation			
Title	Extracting operations defined in a domain concept from a one-to-one-to-many relationship defined between domain objects		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to extract operations that are defined in a domain concept from a one-to-one-to-many relationship that is defined between domain objects		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of relationship from the first node to the middle node </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The expression for resolving the name of operation 8. The expression for resolving the type of operation output 9. The expression for resolving the name of operation input parameter 10. The expression for resolving the type of operation input parameter </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of relationship from the first node to the middle node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The expression for resolving the name of operation 8. The expression for resolving the type of operation output 9. The expression for resolving the name of operation input parameter 10. The expression for resolving the type of operation input parameter
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The output model 3. The first node in the input model 4. The middle node in the input model 5. The last node in the input model 6. The title of relationship from the first node to the middle node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The expression for resolving the name of operation 8. The expression for resolving the type of operation output 9. The expression for resolving the name of operation input parameter 10. The expression for resolving the type of operation input parameter 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Object2Concept/ExtractOperationFromOneToOneToManyRelation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "firstNode": string, "middleNode": string, "lastNode": string, "firstToMiddleNodeRelation": string, "middleToLastNodeRelation": string, "operationNameExpression": string, "operationInputNameExpression": string, "operationInputTypeExpression": string, "operationOutputTypeExpression": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

1.14. Map Object Property to Concept Attribute

Table 21: Pattern Definition: Map Object Property to Concept Attribute

Map Object Property to Concept Attribute					
Title	Mapping the properties of a domain object and its values to the attributes of a domain concept and its values				
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)				
Problem	We want to map the properties and values of a domain object to the attributes and values of a domain concept that has the same name and type as the domain object				
Parameters	<table border="1"><tr><td>1. The input model</td><td>3. The output model</td></tr><tr><td>2. The type of domain object</td><td></td></tr></table>	1. The input model	3. The output model	2. The type of domain object	
1. The input model	3. The output model				
2. The type of domain object					
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Object2Concept/MapObjectPropertyToConceptAttribute Method: POST Request body : { "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "typeOfInstance": string, "outputModel": guid }				

1.15. Replace Association with Relation

Table 22: Pattern Definition: Replace Association with Relation

Replace Association with Relation			
Title	Defining a new relationship in the domain concepts model, based on the existing relationship between domain objects		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to define a new relationship between domain concepts in the output model based on the existing relationship between domain objects in the input model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node 5. The expression for resolving the relationship name in the second model </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the destination of the relationship in the second model 7. The expression for resolving the multiplicity of the relations in the second model 8. The output model (second model) </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node 5. The expression for resolving the relationship name in the second model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the destination of the relationship in the second model 7. The expression for resolving the multiplicity of the relations in the second model 8. The output model (second model)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node 5. The expression for resolving the relationship name in the second model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the destination of the relationship in the second model 7. The expression for resolving the multiplicity of the relations in the second model 8. The output model (second model) 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of the parameters 2, 3, and 4, we identify a set of related objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of tuple (Source, Relation, and Destination). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If there is no concept with the same name and same type as Source in the second model, we will define it. b. We calculate the destination of the relationship based on the information in parameter 6 and the tuple information in step 2, and if there is no such concept in second model, we define it. c. Based on the values of the parameters 5 and 7, we establish a specific relationship with a certain multiplicity between the concepts mentioned in steps (2.a) and (2.b). 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ReplaceAssociationWithRelation Method: POST Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelation": string, "relationNameExpression": string, "relationTargetExpression": string, "multiplicityExpression": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

Example

Table 23: Replace Association with Relation: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	DomainConcept.Concept
DestinationNode	Relation.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelation	hasRelation
RelationNameExpression	DestinationNode.RelationName
RelationTargetExpression	DestinationNode.RelationTarget
MultiplicityExpression	DestinationNode.Multiplicity

Figure 15: Input model

Figure 16: Output model

1.16. Replace Relation with Action

Table 24: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Action

Replace Relation with Action			
Title	Convert a relationship to an operation		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to derive an operation from the relationship defined for a domain object in the first model and define it in the concept corresponding to that object in the second model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The type of instance (domain objects) in the first model 3. The expression for calculating the name of the operation </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The expression for calculating the output of the operation 5. The relationship expressing the inputs of the operation 6. The output model (second model) </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The type of instance (domain objects) in the first model 3. The expression for calculating the name of the operation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The expression for calculating the output of the operation 5. The relationship expressing the inputs of the operation 6. The output model (second model)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The type of instance (domain objects) in the first model 3. The expression for calculating the name of the operation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The expression for calculating the output of the operation 5. The relationship expressing the inputs of the operation 6. The output model (second model) 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of the parameters 2 and 5, we identify a set of domain objects along with a list of operation inputs in the first model and return in the tuple format (domain object, operation inputs). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If there is no concept with the same name and the same type as domain object in the second model, we define it. b. Based on the information of the parameters 3 and 4 as well as the domain object information mentioned in step 2, we specify the name of the operation and its output. c. Based on the values obtained in step (2.b), we create an operation in the domain concept mentioned in step (2.a). 		
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ReplaceRelationWithAction Method: POST Request body : <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "conceptNode": string, "operationNameExpression": string, "operationOutputExpression": string, "operationInputsRelation": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

Example

Table 25: Replace Relation with Action: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
ConceptNode	CommandHandler.Concept
OperationInputsRelation	hasCollaborator
OperationNameExpression	ConceptNode.Name
OperationOutputExpression	“”

Figure 17: Input model

Figure 18: Output model

1.17. Replace Relation with Concept Attribute

Table 26: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Concept Attribute

Replace Relation with Concept Attribute			
Title	Converting a relationship into attributes of a concept		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	An attribute is a metadata that can be assigned to all model elements (concept, property, and operation). We want to extract the attribute name and value based on the information of a relationship and assign it to the desired concept.		
Parameters	<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model </td> <td style="vertical-align: top; padding-left: 20px;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The second model (output model) 6. The expression for resolving the name of the attribute 7. The expression for resolving the value of the attribute </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The second model (output model) 6. The expression for resolving the name of the attribute 7. The expression for resolving the value of the attribute
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node in the first model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The second model (output model) 6. The expression for resolving the name of the attribute 7. The expression for resolving the value of the attribute 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of the parameters 2, 3, and 4, we identify a set of related objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of tuple (Source, Relation, and Destination). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If there is no concept with the same name and same type as Source in the second model, we will define it. b. Based on parameters 6 and 7, and tuple information, we resolve the attribute name and its value. c. For the concept mentioned in step (2.a), we define an attribute with the name and the value obtained in step (2.b). 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ReplaceRelationWithConceptAttribute</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelation": string, "attributeNameExpression": string, "attributeValueExpression": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

Example

Table 27: Replace Relation with Concept Attribute: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	BaseClass.Concept
DestinationNode	Package.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelation	usePackage
AttributeNameExpression	using
AttributeValueExpression	DestinationNode.PackageName

Figure 19: Input model

Figure 20: Output model

1.18. Replace Relation with Generic Property

Table 28: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Generic Property

Replace Relation with Generic Property			
Title	Converting a relation to the concept property		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to define the properties of the concept in the output model based on the information of a relationship between two domain objects in the input model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The output model (second model) 6. The expression for resolving the property name 7. The expression for resolving the property type </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The output model (second model) 6. The expression for resolving the property name 7. The expression for resolving the property type
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The destination node in the first model 4. Title of the relationship from the source node to the destination node 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The output model (second model) 6. The expression for resolving the property name 7. The expression for resolving the property type 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the value of parameters 2, 3, and 4, we identify a set of related objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of the tuple (Source, Relation, and Destination). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If there is no concept with the same name and same type as Source in the second model, we will define it. b. Based on parameters 6 and 7, and tuple information, we resolve the property name and its type. c. For the concept mentioned in step (2.a), we define a property with the name and type obtained in step (2.b). 		
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ReplaceRelationWithGenericProperty Method: POST Request body : <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelation": string, "outputModel": guid, "propertyNameExpression": string, "propertyTypeExpression": string }</pre>		

Example

Table 29: Replace Relation with Generic Property: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	BaseEntity.Concept
DestinationNode	Property.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelation	hasProperty
PropertyNameExpression	DestinationNode.PropertyName
PropertyTypeExpression	DestinationNode.PropertyType

Figure 21: Input model

Figure 22: Output model

1.19. Replace Relation with Operation

Table 30: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Operation

Replace Relation with Operation			
Title	Converting the relation to the operation of a concept		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to define the operation of the corresponding concept in the second model based on the information of a relationship between a chain of domain objects in the first model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The first node in the first model 3. The middle node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node 5. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last nodes </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 7. The expression for resolving the output of the operation 8. The output model (second model) </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The first node in the first model 3. The middle node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node 5. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last nodes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 7. The expression for resolving the output of the operation 8. The output model (second model)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The first node in the first model 3. The middle node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node 5. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last nodes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 7. The expression for resolving the output of the operation 8. The output model (second model) 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of parameters 2, 3, 4, 5, we identify a set of interconnected objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of the tuple (FirstNode, FirstToMiddleNodeRelation, MiddleNode, MiddleToLastNodeRelation, LastNodes). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If there is no concept with the same name and same type as FirstNode in the second model, we will define it. b. Based on the values of parameter 6 and 7 and MiddleNode information, we calculate the name and output of the operation. c. Based on the information of objects corresponding to LastNodes, we extract operation inputs. d. For the concept mentioned in paragraph (2.a), we define an operation with the characteristics obtained in paragraphs (2.b) and (2.c). 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ReplaceRelationWithOperation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "firstNode": string, "middleNode": string, "firstToMiddleNodeRelation": string, "middleToLastNodesRelation": string, "operationNameExpression": string, "operationOutputExpression": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

Examples

Table 31: Replace Relation with Operation: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
FirstNode	ApiController.Concept
MiddleNode	HTTPPost.Endpoint.Concept
FirstToMiddleNodeRelation	hasEndpoint
MiddleToLastNodesRelation	hasRequestBody
OperationNameExpression	MiddleNode.Name
OperationOutputExpression	Task

Figure 23: Input model

Figure 24: Output model

1.20. Replace Relation with Operation Attributes

Table 32: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Operation Attributes

Replace Relation with Operation Attributes			
Title	Converting the relationship into the operation of a concept and assigning the attribute to that operation		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to define the operation of the corresponding concept in the second model based on the information of a relationship between a chain of domain objects in the first model and assign an attribute to this operation according to the information of the chain of objects in the first model.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The first node in the first model 3. The middle node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node 5. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last nodes </td> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 7. The expression for resolving the output of the operation 8. The output model (second model) </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The first node in the first model 3. The middle node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node 5. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last nodes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 7. The expression for resolving the output of the operation 8. The output model (second model)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The first node in the first model 3. The middle node in the first model 4. The title of the relationship from the first node to the middle node 5. The title of the relationship from the middle node to the last nodes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The expression for resolving the name of the operation 7. The expression for resolving the output of the operation 8. The output model (second model) 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of parameters 2, 3, 4, 5, we identify a set of interconnected objects and the relationships between them in the first model in the form of the tuple (FirstNode, FirstToMiddleNodeRelation, MiddleNode, MiddleToLastNodeRelation, LastNodes). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If there is no concept with the same name and same type as FirstNode in the second model, we will define it. b. Based on the values of parameter 6 and 7 and MiddleNode information, we calculate the name and output of the operation. c. Based on the information of objects corresponding to LastNodes, we extract operation inputs. d. For the concept mentioned in paragraph (2.a), we define an operation with the characteristics obtained in paragraphs (2.b) and (2.c). e. For each MiddleNode property, we define an attribute for the operation mentioned in step (2.d) where the name of the attribute is equal to the name of the property and the value of the attribute is equal to the value of the property. 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ReplaceRelationWithOperationAttributes Method: POST Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "firstNode": string, "middleNode": string, "firstToMiddleNodeRelation": string, "middleToLastNodesRelation": string, "operationNameExpression": string, "operationOutputExpression": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

Example

Table 33: Replace Relation with Operation Attributes: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
FirstNode	ApiController.Concept
MiddleNode	HTTPPost.Endpoint.Concept
FirstToMiddleNodeRelation	hasEndpoint
MiddleToLastNodesRelation	hasRequestBody
OperationNameExpression	MiddleNode.Name
OperationOutputExpression	Task

Figure 25: Input model

Figure 26: Output model

1.21. Replace Relation with Property

Table 34: Pattern Definition: Replace Relation with Property

Replace Relation with Property			
Title	Convert the relation to a primitive type property		
Category	Transforming a domain objects model into a domain concepts model (Object2Concept)		
Problem	We want to define the property of a concept in the second model based on the information of a relationship between two domain objects in the input model.		
Parameters	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The title of the relationship between the source node and the nodes expressing the properties </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The output model (second model) </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The title of the relationship between the source node and the nodes expressing the properties 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The output model (second model)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model (first model) 2. The source node in the first model 3. The title of the relationship between the source node and the nodes expressing the properties 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. The output model (second model) 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of parameters 2 and 3, we identify a set of related objects in the tuple format (Source, Properties). 2. For each tuple identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. If there is no concept with the same name and type as Source in the second model, we will define it. b. Based on tuple information, we get the property name and its type. c. For the concept mentioned in step (2.a), we define an property with the name and type obtained in step (2.b). 		
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/Object2Concept/ReplaceRelationWithProperty Method: POST Request body : <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelation": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

Example

Table 35: Replace Relation with Property: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	BaseEntity.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelation	hasProperty

Figure 27: Input model

Figure 28: Output model

1.22. Copy Upstream Node Property to Downstream Node Relation

Table 36: Pattern Definition: Copy Upstream Node Property to Downstream Node Relation

Copy Upstream Node Property to Downstream Node Relation			
Title	Converting properties of upstream model concepts to objects and relationships between them in the downstream model		
Category	Combining a model of domain objects with a model of domain concepts based on Relational Dimension (RelationalDimension)		
Problem	We want to transform the properties of a domain concept in the upstream model into domain objects and the relationships between them in the downstream model so that we can make it more precise at a lower level of abstraction.		
Parameters	<table border="1"> <tr> <td> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The upstream model of domain concepts (input model) 2. The downstream model of domain objects (input and output model) 3. The source node in the downstream model 4. The destination node in the upstream model </td> <td> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The title of the Relational Dimension from the source node to the destination node 6. The title of the relationship from the source node to the new objects resulting from the transformation, in the downstream model </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The upstream model of domain concepts (input model) 2. The downstream model of domain objects (input and output model) 3. The source node in the downstream model 4. The destination node in the upstream model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The title of the Relational Dimension from the source node to the destination node 6. The title of the relationship from the source node to the new objects resulting from the transformation, in the downstream model
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The upstream model of domain concepts (input model) 2. The downstream model of domain objects (input and output model) 3. The source node in the downstream model 4. The destination node in the upstream model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The title of the Relational Dimension from the source node to the destination node 6. The title of the relationship from the source node to the new objects resulting from the transformation, in the downstream model 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of the parameters 2 and 3, we retrieve the domain objects created from the source node in the downstream model. 2. For each of the objects identified in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Based on the value of parameter 5 and the object information mentioned in step 2, we calculate the destination of the relation in the upstream model and retrieve the concept corresponding to it in the upstream model. b. For each of the properties of the concept identified in the previous step, we create a domain object in the downstream model (if this object does not exist) whose name is equal to the name of the property and its type is equal to the type of that property. c. Based on the value of parameter 6, we establish a relationship from the object mentioned in step 2 to the object mentioned in step (2.b). 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/RelationalDimension/CopyUpstreamNodePropertyToDownstreamNodeRelation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downStreamModel": guid, "upStreamModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelationalDimension": string, "relationName": string }</pre>		

Example

Table 37: Copy Upstream Node Property to Downstream Node Relation: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	BaseClass.Concept
DestinationNode	BaseEntity.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelationalDimension	represent
RelationName	hasProperty

Figure 29: Input model

Figure 30: Output model

1.23. Copy Upstream Node Relation to Downstream Node Relation

Table 38: Pattern Definition: Copy Upstream Node Relation to Downstream Node Relation

Copy Upstream Node Relation to Downstream Node Relation									
Title	Converting relationships between concepts in the upstream model to objects and relationships between them in the downstream model								
Category	Combining a model of domain objects with a model of domain concepts based on Relational Dimension (RelationalDimension)								
Problem	We want to transform the domain concepts with a certain relationship in the upstream model, under a certain relationship, into domain objects and the relationships between them in the downstream model, so that we can make it more precise at a lower level of abstraction.								
Parameters	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. The upstream model of domain concepts (input model)</td> <td>5. The title of the Relational Dimension from the source node to the destination node</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. The downstream model of domain objects (input and output model)</td> <td>6. The title of the relationship from the source node in the downstream model</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. The source node in the downstream model</td> <td>7. The title of the relationship from the destination node in the upstream model</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. The destination node in the upstream model</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1. The upstream model of domain concepts (input model)	5. The title of the Relational Dimension from the source node to the destination node	2. The downstream model of domain objects (input and output model)	6. The title of the relationship from the source node in the downstream model	3. The source node in the downstream model	7. The title of the relationship from the destination node in the upstream model	4. The destination node in the upstream model	
1. The upstream model of domain concepts (input model)	5. The title of the Relational Dimension from the source node to the destination node								
2. The downstream model of domain objects (input and output model)	6. The title of the relationship from the source node in the downstream model								
3. The source node in the downstream model	7. The title of the relationship from the destination node in the upstream model								
4. The destination node in the upstream model									
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the values of parameters 2 and 3, we retrieve the domain objects created from the source node in the downstream model. 2. For each of the objects identified in the previous step: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Based on the value of parameters 4 and 5 of the problem model and the object information mentioned in step 2, we calculate the destination of the relationship in the upstream model and retrieve the corresponding concept (destination node) in the upstream model. b. Based on the information of the previous step, we identify other concepts of the upstream model that there is the relationship (parameter 7) from the destination node to them. c. For each concept identified in the upstream model, in step (2.b) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i. In the downstream model, we create a domain object that has the same name and type as that concept. ii. Based on the value of parameter 6, we establish a relationship from the object mentioned in step 2 to the object mentioned in step (2.c.i). 								
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/RelationalDimension/CopyUpstreamNodeRelationToDownstreamNodeRelation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downStreamModel": guid, "upStreamModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelationalDimension": string, "upStreamNodeRelation": string, "downStreamNodeRelation": string }</pre>								

1.24. Merge Upstream Node Property with Downstream Node Relation

Table 39: Pattern Definition: Merge Upstream Node Property with Downstream Node Relation

Merge Upstream Node Property with Downstream Node Relation			
Title	Combining properties and relations of upstream model concepts with relations of domain objects in the downstream model, in the form of new properties in the output model		
Category	Combining a model of domain objects with a model of domain concepts based on Relational Dimension (RelationalDimension)		
Problem	We want to merge the properties and relationships between entities in two models with different abstraction levels into one output model.		
Parameters	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model) 2. Downstream domain objects model (input model) 3. The source node in the downstream model </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model 5. The title of the relationship from the source node to other objects of the downstream model 6. Output model </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model) 2. Downstream domain objects model (input model) 3. The source node in the downstream model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model 5. The title of the relationship from the source node to other objects of the downstream model 6. Output model
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model) 2. Downstream domain objects model (input model) 3. The source node in the downstream model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model 5. The title of the relationship from the source node to other objects of the downstream model 6. Output model 		
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the value of parameter 3, we retrieve the domain objects created from the source node in the downstream model. 2. For each of the objects retrieved in the previous step, do following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. In the output model, we create a domain concept with the same name and type as the object mentioned in step 2. b. We identify all the domain objects in the downstream model with which the object mentioned in step 2 has a specific relationship (parameter 5), and for each of these objects, we define a property with the same name and type as that object, for the concept mentioned in step (2.a). c. Based on the value of parameter 4, we retrieve the domain concept mentioned in the upstream model. d. For each property of the concept mentioned in step (2.c), we define a property with the same specifications for the concept mentioned in step (2.a). e. For each relation defined from the concept referred to in step (2.c), we define a property corresponding to the specification of the relationship for the concept referred to in step (2.a). 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/RelationalDimension/MergeUpstreamNodePropertyWithDownStreamNodeRelation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downStreamModel": guid, "upStreamModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelationalDimension": string, "sourceNodeRelationName": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>		

Example

Table 40: Merge Upstream Node Property with Downstream Node Relation: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
SourceNode	BaseEntity.Concept
SourceToDestinationRelationalDimension	represent
SourceNodeRelationName	hasEntityId

Figure 31: Input model

Figure 32: Output model

1.25. Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node

Table 41: Pattern Definition: Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node

Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node											
Title	Combining the operations and properties of upstream domain concepts model and downstream domain objects models, in the form of the properties and operations of new concepts in the output model										
Category	Combining a model of domain objects with a model of domain concepts based on Relational Dimension (RelationalDimension)										
Problem	We want to merge the properties and operations of the elements in two models with different abstraction levels, depending on the user's choice, in the form of an output model.										
Parameters	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr> <td>1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)</td> <td>6. Should the properties of the upstream concept be transferred to the output model?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Downstream domain objects model (input model)</td> <td>7. Should the operation of the upstream concept be transferred to the output model?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. The source node in the downstream model</td> <td>8. Should the properties of the source node be transferred to the output model?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model</td> <td>9. Should the operation of the source node be transferred to the output model?</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5. Output model</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)	6. Should the properties of the upstream concept be transferred to the output model?	2. Downstream domain objects model (input model)	7. Should the operation of the upstream concept be transferred to the output model?	3. The source node in the downstream model	8. Should the properties of the source node be transferred to the output model?	4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model	9. Should the operation of the source node be transferred to the output model?	5. Output model	
1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)	6. Should the properties of the upstream concept be transferred to the output model?										
2. Downstream domain objects model (input model)	7. Should the operation of the upstream concept be transferred to the output model?										
3. The source node in the downstream model	8. Should the properties of the source node be transferred to the output model?										
4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model	9. Should the operation of the source node be transferred to the output model?										
5. Output model											
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the value of parameter 3, we retrieve the domain objects created from the source node in the downstream model 2. For each of the objects retrieved in the previous step, do the following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. In the output model, we create a domain concept with the same name and type as the object mentioned in step 2. b. If the value of parameter 8 is true, for each source node property, define a similar property for the concept referred to in step (2.a). c. If the value of parameter 9 is true, for each operation in the source node, define a similar operation for the concept referred to in step (2.a). d. Based on the value of parameter 4, retrieve the concept referred to in the upstream model. e. If the value of parameter 6 is true, for each property of the concept referred to in step (2.d), define a similar property for the concept referred to in step (2.a). f. If the value of parameter 7 is true, for each operation in the concept referred to in step (2.d), define a similar operation for the concept referred to in step (2.a). 										
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/RelationalDimension/MergeUpstreamNodeWithDownStreamNode</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downStreamModel": guid, "upStreamModel": guid, "downStreamNode": string, "relationalDimension": string, "copyUpstreamNodeProperty": bool, "copyUpsteramNodeOperation": bool, "copyDownstreamNodeProperty": bool, "copyDownstreamNodeOperation": bool, "outputModel": guid}</pre>										

Example

Table 42: Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
DownStreamNode	BaseClass.Concept
RelationalDimension	represent
CopyUpStreamNodeProperty	True
CopyUpStreamNodeOperation	True
CopyDownStreamNodeProperty	True
CopyDownStreamNodeOperation	True

Figure 33: Input model

Figure 34: Output model

1.26. Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node Property as Attribute

Table 43: Pattern Definition: Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node Property as Attribute

Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node Property as Attribute							
Title	Combining the operations and properties of the upstream domain concepts model and downstream domain objects models, in the form of operations, properties and attributes of new concepts in the output model						
Category	Combining a model of domain objects with a model of domain concepts based on Relational Dimension (RelationalDimension)						
Problem	We want to merge the properties and operations of the elements of two models in different abstraction levels in the form of properties, operations and attributes of new concepts in one output model, so that the properties of the elements of the downstream model are defined in the form of attributes of the new concept in the output model.						
Parameters	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)</td> <td>4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Downstream domain objects model (input model)</td> <td>5. Output model</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. The source node in the downstream model</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)	4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model	2. Downstream domain objects model (input model)	5. Output model	3. The source node in the downstream model	
1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)	4. A relational dimension from the source node to the domain concepts in the upstream model						
2. Downstream domain objects model (input model)	5. Output model						
3. The source node in the downstream model							
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the value of parameter 3, we retrieve the domain objects created from the source node in the downstream model. 2. For each of the objects retrieved in the previous step, do the following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. In the output model, we create a domain concept with the same name and type as the object mentioned in step 2. b. For each property of the object mentioned in step 2, define an attribute, the same name as that property and having a value equal to the value of that property, for the concept mentioned in step (2.a). c. For each operation on the source node, define a similar operation for the concept mentioned to in step (2.a). d. Based on the value of parameter 4, retrieve the concept referred to in the upstream model. e. For each property of the concept mentioned in step (2.d), define a similar property for the concept mentioned in step (2.a). f. For each operation in the concept mentioned in step (2.d), define a similar operation for the concept mentioned in step (2.a). 						
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/RelationalDimension/MergeUpstreamNodeWithDownStreamNodePropertyAsAttribute Method: POST Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downStreamModel": guid, "upStreamModel": guid, "downStreamNode": string, "relationalDimension": string, "outputModel": guid }</pre>						

Example

Table 44: Merge Upstream Node with Downstream Node Property as Attribute: Pattern Instance Parameter Values

Parameter	Value
DownStreamNode	BaseClass.Concept
RelationalDimension	represent

Figure 35: Input model

Figure 36: Output model

1.27. Replace Relational Dimension with Source Node Relation

Table 45: Pattern Definition: Replace Relational Dimension with Source Node Relation

Replace Relational Dimension with Source Node Relation									
Title	Replacing the relational dimension between the downstream model and the upstream model with new objects and relationships in the downstream model								
Category	Combining a model of domain objects with a model of domain concepts based on Relational Dimension (RelationalDimension)								
Problem	We want to create a new domain object with the same name of the concept in the upstream model, and in a specific relationship with other objects in the downstream model.								
Parameters	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)</td> <td>5. A relational dimension from the downstream model to the upstream model</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. Downstream domain objects model(input and output model)</td> <td>6. The title of the relationship in the downstream model</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. The source node in the downstream model</td> <td>7. The destination of the relationship in the downstream model</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4. The destination node in the upstream model</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)	5. A relational dimension from the downstream model to the upstream model	2. Downstream domain objects model(input and output model)	6. The title of the relationship in the downstream model	3. The source node in the downstream model	7. The destination of the relationship in the downstream model	4. The destination node in the upstream model	
1. Upstream domain concepts model (input model)	5. A relational dimension from the downstream model to the upstream model								
2. Downstream domain objects model(input and output model)	6. The title of the relationship in the downstream model								
3. The source node in the downstream model	7. The destination of the relationship in the downstream model								
4. The destination node in the upstream model									
Solution	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Based on the value of the parameter 3, we retrieve the desired domain objects in the downstream model. 2. For each object retrieved in the previous step, do the following steps: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Based on the value of parameter 5, we identify the concept referred to in the upstream model. b. In the downstream model, we create a new object whose name is equal to the name of the concept mentioned in step (2.a) and whose type is equal to the value of parameter 7. c. In the downstream model, based on the value of parameter 6, we establish a relationship between the object mentioned in step 2 and the object created in step (2.b). 								
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/RelationalDimension/ReplaceRelationalDimensionWithSourceNodeRelation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downStreamModel": guid, "upStreamModel": guid, "sourceNode": string, "destinationNode": string, "sourceToDestinationRelationalDimension": string, "relationName": string, "relationTarget": string }</pre>								

1.28. Set Higher Dimension Relation

Table 46: Pattern Definition: Set Higher Dimension Relation

Set Higher Dimension Relation			
Title	Setting the relational dimension of the domain objects of the downstream model at the lower level of abstraction, based on the domain objects of the upstream model at a higher level		
Category	Combining a model of domain objects with a model of domain concepts based on Relational Dimension (RelationalDimension)		
Problem	We want to set the relational dimension of the domain objects of the downstream model at a lower level of abstraction based on the domain objects of the upstream model at a higher level.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The upstream model 2. The downstream model 3. The type of domain object in the upstream model 4. The type of domain object in the downstream model </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The expression for resolving the title of the relational dimension 6. The expression for resolving the target of the relational dimension </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The upstream model 2. The downstream model 3. The type of domain object in the upstream model 4. The type of domain object in the downstream model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The expression for resolving the title of the relational dimension 6. The expression for resolving the target of the relational dimension
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The upstream model 2. The downstream model 3. The type of domain object in the upstream model 4. The type of domain object in the downstream model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. The expression for resolving the title of the relational dimension 6. The expression for resolving the target of the relational dimension 		
How to use	<p>Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/RelationalDimension/SetHigherDimensionRelation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "upstreamConcept": string, "downstreamConcept": string, "relationNameExpression": string, "relationTargetExpression": string, "upstreamModel": guid, "downstreamModel": guid }</pre>		

1.29. Append Line of String for Each One to Many Relation

Table 47: Pattern Definition: Append Line of String for Each One to Many Relation

Append Line of String for Each One to Many Relation			
Title	Converting the information of related objects in a one-to-many relationship into a string and inserting it into the text		
Category	Transforming a model to text (Model2Text)		
Problem	We want to take the information of related objects in a one-to-many relationship and convert it into a string. Then, we want to insert this string into the text at the specific position.		
Parameters	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The source node in the input model 3. The destination node in the input model 4. The template Id 5. The template file Id 6. The marker inside template file 7. The expression for resolving the value of the string that should be inserted 8. The output model 9. The concept of file in the output model </td> <td style="vertical-align: top; width: 50%;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. The expression for resolving the name of a domain object that its type is denoted in the parameter 9 11. The file name property 12. The expression for resolving the value of the file name property 13. The file extension property 14. The expression for resolving the value of the file extension property 15. The file relative path property 16. The expression for resolving the value of the file relative path property </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The source node in the input model 3. The destination node in the input model 4. The template Id 5. The template file Id 6. The marker inside template file 7. The expression for resolving the value of the string that should be inserted 8. The output model 9. The concept of file in the output model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. The expression for resolving the name of a domain object that its type is denoted in the parameter 9 11. The file name property 12. The expression for resolving the value of the file name property 13. The file extension property 14. The expression for resolving the value of the file extension property 15. The file relative path property 16. The expression for resolving the value of the file relative path property
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The input model 2. The source node in the input model 3. The destination node in the input model 4. The template Id 5. The template file Id 6. The marker inside template file 7. The expression for resolving the value of the string that should be inserted 8. The output model 9. The concept of file in the output model 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. The expression for resolving the name of a domain object that its type is denoted in the parameter 9 11. The file name property 12. The expression for resolving the value of the file name property 13. The file extension property 14. The expression for resolving the value of the file extension property 15. The file relative path property 16. The expression for resolving the value of the file relative path property 		
How to use	<p>Uri: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Model2Text/AppendLineForEachOneToManyRelation</p> <p>Method: POST</p> <p>Request body :</p> <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "inputModel": guid, "source": string, "destination": string, "sourceToDestinationRelation": string, "templateArchiveId": string, "templateFileId": string, "marker": string, "valueExpression": string, "outputModel": guid "fileConcept": string, "instanceNameExpression": string, "fileContentProperty": string, "fileNameProeprty": string, "fileNameValueExpression": string, "fileExtensionProperty": string, "fileExtensionValue": string, "fileRelativePathProeprty": string, "fileRelativePathValue": string, }</pre>		

1.30. Generate C# Code of Class Concept

Table 48: Pattern Definition: Generate C# Code of Class Concept

Generate C# Code of Class Concept							
Title	Converting the information of a concept corresponding to a class to the definition code of the Class in C# language						
Category	Transforming a model to text (Model2Text)						
Problem	We want to take the information of a concept that corresponds to a class and convert it into the definition code of the Class in C# language.						
Parameters	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>1. The downstream model</td> <td>4. The title of relational dimension</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. The upstream model</td> <td>5. The content property of the</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. The downstream node in the downstream model</td> <td>downstream node to store the result</td> </tr> </table>	1. The downstream model	4. The title of relational dimension	2. The upstream model	5. The content property of the	3. The downstream node in the downstream model	downstream node to store the result
1. The downstream model	4. The title of relational dimension						
2. The upstream model	5. The content property of the						
3. The downstream node in the downstream model	downstream node to store the result						
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Model2Text/GenerateCSharpCodeOfClassConcept Method: POST Request body : <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downstreamModel": guid, "upstreamModel": guid, "downstreamNode": string, "relationalDimension": string, "contentProperty": string, }</pre>						

1.31. Generate C# Code of Interface Concept

Table 49: Pattern Definition: Generate C# Code of Interface Concept

Generate C# Code of Interface Concept							
Title	Converting the information of a concept corresponding to an interface to the definition code of the Interface in C# language						
Category	Transforming a model to text (Model2Text)						
Problem	We want to take the information of a concept that corresponds to an interface and convert it into the definition code of the Interface in C# language.						
Parameters	<table border="0"> <tr> <td>1. The downstream model</td> <td>4. The title of relational dimension</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2. The upstream model</td> <td>5. The content property of the downstream node to store the result</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3. The downstream node in the downstream model</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1. The downstream model	4. The title of relational dimension	2. The upstream model	5. The content property of the downstream node to store the result	3. The downstream node in the downstream model	
1. The downstream model	4. The title of relational dimension						
2. The upstream model	5. The content property of the downstream node to store the result						
3. The downstream node in the downstream model							
How to use	Url: http://modeltransformations-service/TransformationPattern/Model2Text/GenerateCSharpCodeOfInterfaceConcept Method: POST Request body : <pre>{ "coordinationId": guid, "stepId": guid, "downstreamModel": guid, "upstreamModel": guid, "downstreamNode": string, "relationalDimension": string, "contentProperty": string, }</pre>						